

List of CST related standards

SOLARIZE D2.5 – WP2 Task 4

List of the existing CSP/CST related standards, involvement of the partners

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is targeted to:

- **Any academic or industrial in the concentrated solar energy** field, especially in Europe or interested in the European market, from newcomers to experienced developers,
- Partners from European project SOLARIZE and ERIC EU-SOLARIS.

This report notably includes (see table of contents for completeness):

1. Overall presentation of [how international/European standards are made \(page 9\)](#), and by [which structures \(page 13\)](#);
2. Listing the [standards for the CST/CSP](#) field for application in Europe, as industrial developer or academic researcher (page 24);
3. [Presence of SOLARIZE and EU-SOLARIS](#) individuals in the international standardization process: 17% of worldwide contributors (page 32);
4. Among annexes:
 - a. Listing [standards originating for other fields](#) but which can be relevant for CST/CSP developments or to develop CST/CSP dedicated standards (page 34);
 - b. [CSP/CST national standards existing in non-SOLARIZE countries](#) (page 38).

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Focus has been given to [IEC 62862](#) set of standards and its related technical committee [IEC/TC 117](#) as they are the most relevant for EU-SOLARIS main targeted industrial international market with concentrated solar energy.

Geographic scope: focus on SOLARIZE and EU-SOLARIS

The European project SOLARIZE aims to develop the ERIC EU-SOLARIS, including with possible new members to the ERIC, both organizations and countries. This deliverable focuses on this larger group of partners and is neither limited to EU-SOLARIS nor SOLARIZE.

It covers most but not all CSP/CST activities in Europe.

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2. Main abbreviations

This table excludes most organization acronyms, except at international and European levels.

CEN	European Committee for Standardization (from French, <i>Comité Européen de Normalisation</i>)
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
CST	Concentrated Solar Thermal
EN	European standard (from German, <i>Europäische Norm</i>)
IEA	International Energy Agency
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
SHIP	Solar Heat integration in Industrial Processes
STE	Solar Thermal Electricity
TC	Technical Committee
WG	Working Group

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3. Text conventions

Disclaimer: “quoted text without edition” is displayed in this style.

The naming of the standards and committees has been reproduced as designed by their organization: notice that the scheme may differ from country to country or at international level. European schemes are very homogenous except for spacing and “/” usage, but for example the scheme is quite different in the USA at ASTM standardization organization.

Care has been given to avoid word splitting of the standard references, except in the tables for columns compactness.

4. The standardization process

The standardization process is a structured, consensus-driven framework designed to develop international standards that address global technical, safety, or operational needs.

The process for international standards is itself standardized and is similar at European and national levels: steps, decisions-making... Acronyms and details in this chapter are those applicable for ISO/IEC and CEN/CENELEC, there may be differences for standards originating at national levels, at least translation in the native language. Notice that US standards have rather different acronyms, but similar hierarchical organization and operation principles.

The main steps, detailed thereafter, are:

1. Identification of need
2. Proposition of a new standard
3. Drafting the standard
4. Review at committee level
5. Public comment stage
6. Final approval and publication
7. Periodic evaluation: continued, revised or removed

4.1. Identification of need

A standard is typically initiated due to a perceived gap in existing standards (e.g. new technology, testing protocol, regulatory requirements, or industry challenges). This gap is shown by the industry and/or academics to their national standardization organisation, which drops it, deal with it by creating a new working group or transferring it to an existing committee, or transfer it to a better suited organisation (international level, field of topics...).

Proposals often arise from workshops, conferences (such as SolarPACES) for CST/CSP, or direct requests by industries/national bodies.

4.2. Proposing a new standard

To create a new international standard, any National Standards Bodies (NSB), technical committee, stakeholder, or research consortium can

submit a new work technical item proposal (NWIP) to ISO/IEC. The proposal must include: the scope and purpose of the standard, potential users and benefits, and an optional preliminary draft. If approved by a majority vote (~60–75% approval from NSBs), the work item is authorized, and either a Working Group (WG) or a Task Group (TG) is established at ISO, or a Project Team (PT) at IEC, with a designated secretary. Members are volunteer individuals accepted by the secretary of the committee and standardisation body, in agreement to any policy existing such as enough diversity of organizations, and obviously being expert in the topic.

4.3. Drafting stage

The WG/TG develops an initial draft under the guidance of a chair and convener. Early-stage outputs may include:

- Informal consensus documents from technical workshops, such as:
 - ISO/IEC Technical Reports (TR);
 - ISO/IEC Publicly Available Specifications (PAS);
 - SolarPACES or European projects workshops and their deliverables; ...
- Guidelines: Non-normative documents that outline best practices or preliminary ideas for future standards.

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4.4. Committee review stage

The first formal draft is called a Committee Draft (CD). Circulated to all NSBs, the CD undergoes technical review and feedback from stakeholders. Major revisions may result in multiple iterations of the CD before moving forward.

4.5. Public comment stage

A revised draft becomes a Draft International Standard (DIS) or Final DIS (FDIS) depending on maturity. The DIS is open for public comment globally (typically 3–6 months), allowing wider input beyond NSBs. Comments are addressed, and the document is updated to reflect consensus.

4.6. Final approval and publication

After incorporating feedback, the final version becomes a Final Draft International Standard (FDIS). NSBs vote on adoption, standards require at

least 2/3 approval from participating members. If approved, the standard is published with an international reference number (e.g., ISO 9001:2015).

4.7. Adoption as national standards

Once an international standard is finalized, NSBs may adopt it into national standards. Adoption can be:

- Identical: directly using the international text (e.g. UNE-EN ISO 9001 in Spain or NF ISO 9001 in France).
- Modified: including minor adjustments to align with local requirements.
- Referred in legislation: national laws may mandate compliance with specific international standards.

4.8. Standards evolution and removal

Once a standard has been published, it undergoes regular evaluations by its committee for market relevance to meet the evolution of the needs of the industry.

This periodic evaluation can lead to a new edition of the standard (with all the stages above: from draft, review, comments...), evolution of the standard (merging with another one, revision from one type to another...), or eventually its removal.

These decisions are made by public vote of the committee after discussions, with thresholds depending on the organization.

4.9. Participation to a standardization committee

Participation generally requires contacting the committee secretary, typically with a co-opting from existing individual members. If approved, this participation requires a paying subscription per individual or per represented organization, depending on the standardization body.

4.10. Official languages for international standards

The three official languages of ISO are English, French, and Russian.

The three official languages of CEN and CENELEC are English, French, and German.

4.11. The standardization process as one picture

Below is a summary from the Greek standardization organization ELOT.

5. Standardization organizations

The organizations directly relevant in Europe are listed and shortly described thereafter. For other CSP/CST markets worldwide, other national organizations should be cited: ASTM (USA), CSA (China)... see [Annex 2](#).

The organizations described thereafter have been listed by their geographical perimeter:

1. International levels: ISO and IEC ; IEA and SolarPACES ; CIE
2. European level: CEN and CENELEC
3. National levels

5.1. International levels: ISO and IEC

Those 2 international organizations are dedicated to standardization, including for CSP/CST:

- ISO (International Organization for Standardization) is a global independent organization that develops voluntary consensus-based standards across various industries.
- IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission): Focuses on electrical, electronic, and related technologies.

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Their organization is similar, with technical committees dedicated to a topic or field of topics, with the aim of creating, publishing, updating, removing international standards. Those standards are then applied as is, or adapted for national application in a country (translation, conformity to national laws...).

5.2. International levels: IEA and SolarPACES

At international level, for CSP/CST standardization activities, one must also cite SolarPACES from IEA:

- The IEA (International Energy Agency) is an intergovernmental organization focused on energy policy cooperation and analysis across all fuels and technologies. Founded in 1974 to address oil security for OECD, it now promotes sustainability with expanded cooperation since 2015 to major emerging countries.
- SolarPACES (Solar Power And Chemical Energy Systems), operating under IEA's Technology Collaboration Programme, is dedicated to

research and advancements in concentrating solar power (CSP) and related technologies. The main fields are solar thermal electricity (STE), high-temperature CST for industrial process heat decarbonisation, solar thermochemistry for fuel production, thermal storage for dispatchable energy production...

5.3. International level: CIE

The CIE, or Commission Internationale de l'Éclairage (International Commission on Illumination), is the international authority on light, illumination, colour, and colour spaces; including reference solar spectra.

5.4. European level: CEN and CENELEC

CEN (European Committee for Standardization) and CENELEC (electrotechnical standards) harmonize regional standards across Europe, working closely with national standardization bodies (NSBs). These European standards often align with or derive from ISO/IEC's global standards, which NSBs adopt into their national frameworks (e.g. NF ISO in France or UNE-EN ISO in Spain). Thus, CEN/CENELEC act as intermediaries between global ISO/IEC standards and European NSBs, ensuring regional harmonization while maintaining consistency with international norms.

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CEN's and CENELEC's standards are often adopted as European standards (EN) and are referenced as "EN IEC" when they are based on IEC standards.

CEN and CENELEC can also be an entry point for a new standard project. For example, consider CWA 17726:2021 "High temperature accelerated ageing of advanced ceramic specimens for solar receivers and other applications under concentrated solar radiation". This CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) originated directly from the European project NEXTOWER coordinated by Italy's ENEA (H2020 GA #721045) thanks to the support from Spain's UNE.

5.5. National Standardization Bodies for SOLARIZE

Below is the list of national standardization bodies (NSB) for each country for EU-SOLARIS ERIC and SOLARIZE partners.

Notice that Germany has an active entity dedicated to electrotechnical applications (DKE), in addition to a general organization (DIN), mirroring IEC and ISO specialization at national level.

In the case of Portugal, beside the NSB, there are sectorial standardization bodies (ONS). For electrotechnical applications, the ONS is IEP (the Portuguese Electrotechnical Institute), linked to the IEC.

Table 1 – National standardization bodies for SOLARIZE countries

SOLARIZE country	National standardization bodies (NSB)
Cyprus	Cyprus Organization for Standardization (CYS) <i>Κυπριακός Οργανισμός Τυποποίησης</i> https://www.cys.org.cy/en/
France	French Standardization Association (AFNOR) <i>Association française de normalisation</i> https://www.afnor.org/en/
Germany	German Institute for Standardization (DIN) <i>Deutsches Institut für Normung</i> https://www.din.de/en
	German Commission for Electrotechnical, Electronic & Information Technologies (DKE) <i>Deutsche Kommission Elektrotechnik, Elektronik und Informationstechnik</i> https://www.dke.de/en
Greece	Hellenic Organization for Standardization (ELOT) <i>Ελληνικός Οργανισμός Τυποποίησης (ΕΛΟΤ)</i> https://elot.gr/en/
Italy	Italian National Unification (UNI) <i>Ente Nazionale Italiano di Unificazione</i> https://www.uni.com/en/
Portugal	Portuguese Quality Institute (IPQ) <i>Instituto Português da Qualidade</i> https://www.ipq.pt/en/
	Portuguese Electrotechnical Institute (IEP) <i>Instituto Electrotécnico Português</i> https://www.iep.pt/en/
Spain	Spanish Association for Standardization (UNE) <i>Asociación Española de Normalización</i> https://www.en.une.org

SOLARIZE country	National standardization bodies (NSB)
Turkey	Turkish Standards Institution (TSE) <i>Türk Standardları Enstitüsü</i> https://www.tse.org.tr/

6. Technical committees for CSP/CST for Europe, for SOLARIZE

Technical committees (TC) are the structured groups handling the standardization process for a given topic or field of topics.

Thereafter are listed the identified technical committees relevant to EU-SOLARIS ERIC and SOLARIZE partners, focused on CSP & CST fields including STE, at international and national levels.

6.1. International: IEA SolarPACES task groups

IEA SolarPACES is dedicated to concentrated solar energy. It has task groups to develop guidelines, estimate trends, build databases... The work from those task groups or from the workshop they organize can evolve to proposed standards or proposed drafts. There are five tasks currently being undertaken by the SolarPACES Programme, all relevant for this deliverable:

- Task I: Solar Thermal Electric Systems.
- Task II: Solar Chemistry Research.
- Task III: Solar Technology and Advanced Applications.
- Task IV: Solar Heat for Industrial Processes.
- Task V: Solar Resource Assessment and Forecasting.

Public website of IEA SolarPACES tasks

<https://www.solarpaces.org/solarpaces-tasks/>

6.2. International: IEA SHC task groups

In addition to SolarPACES, IEA hosts the IEA Solar Heating and Cooling programme (IEA SHC), dealing with solar energy for buildings and industry, mostly but not limited to non-concentrating solar technologies. The IEA Solar Heating and Cooling Technology Collaboration Programme (IEA SHC TCP) develops projects (Tasks) to study various aspects of solar heating and cooling, an identical organization to the SolarPACES tasks. Among

those tasks, some are relevant for CSP/CST, such as the completed IEA SHC Task 64 “Solar Process Heat”, for building and industry, up to 400–500°C, which is a collaborative work with SolarPACES.

<https://task64.iea-shc.org/>

6.3. International: ISO/TC 180 – Solar energy

ISO/TC 180 scope

At ISO level, the technical committee TC 180 is dedicated to solar energy, concentrating or not, except for electricity production (deferred to IEC/TC 82 and IEC/TC 117, see lower). Other solar applications (buildings, aerospace...) are dealt with by other committees.

[ISO/TC 180 handles] “*standardization in the field of solar energy utilization in space and water heating, cooling, industrial process heating and air conditioning. This includes developing standards on the instrumentation and procedures used for measuring solar energy and solar measurement.*”

List of existing subcommittees:

- SO/TC 180/AHG 1 - Measurement of CO₂
- **ISO/TC 180/SC 1 - Climate - Measurement and data**
- ISO/TC 180/SC 4 - Systems - Thermal performance, reliability and durability
- ISO/TC 180/SC 5 - Collectors and other components
- ISO/TC 180/WG 1 - Nomenclature
- ISO/TC 180/WG 2 - Materials
- ISO/TC 180/WG 3 - Collector components and materials
- ISO/TC 180/WG 4 - Solar collectors

Subcommittee ISO/TC 180/SC 1 is especially relevant for CSP/CST as it handles solar resource assessment and related ground sensors calibration procedures: pyrhemeters, pyranometers...

The “solar collectors” handled by ISO/TC 180 subcommittee (SC) and working groups (WG) are mostly non-concentrating systems, but not exclusively. The related standards can therefore be of interest for CSP/CST, as some technologies, conditions or methods are similar.

Public website for ISO/TC 180

<https://www.iso.org/committee/54018.html>

6.4. International: IEC/TC 82 – PV, CPV

IEC/TC 82 scope

At IEC level, the technical committee IEC/TC 82 is dedicated to PV (photovoltaics) which includes CPV (concentrated photovoltaics):

“To prepare international standards for systems of photovoltaic conversion of solar energy into electrical energy and for all the elements in the entire photovoltaic energy system. In this context, the concept “photovoltaic energy system” includes the entire field from light input to a photovoltaic cell to and including the interface with the electrical system(s) to which energy is supplied.

NOTE: It is recognized that there is some common interest between TC 47 and TC 82, therefore these two committees shall maintain liaison.”

Public website for IEC/TC 82

https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:7:706159260178935:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:1276,25

IEC/TC 82 participants

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Countries can be either full member or associate members to IEC. The main restriction for IEC associate members: they cannot occupy management positions and functions within the IEC and do not have voting rights in the IEC General Assembly. This status has therefore no impact on a TC participation and operation.

For each TC or WG (working group), each country has either P or O status:

- P-Members are full members who can actively participate in any technical committee or subcommittee.
- O-Members are observers who follow the work of a particular committee without committing to active participation.

Table 2 – IEC/TC 82: participating countries from SOLARIZE

SOLARIZE country	P/O status @ IEC/TC 82	IEC membership
Cyprus	Not participating	Full member
France	P-member	Full member

SOLARIZE country	P/O status @ IEC/TC 82	IEC membership
Germany	P-member	Full member
Greece	P-member	Full member
Italy	P-member	Full member
Portugal	P-member	Full member
Spain	P-member	Full member
Turkey	O-member	Full member

Whatever their status, here is the complete list of all 58 members to IEC/TC 82: Algeria, Argentina, Australia, Austria, Bahrain, Belgium, Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, Chile, China, Côte D'Ivoire, Czech Republic, Denmark, Egypt, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, India, Indonesia, Iran, Israel, Italy, Japan, Kenya, Korea, Malaysia, Mexico, Morocco, Netherlands, New Zealand, Nigeria, Norway, Oman, Philippines, Poland, Portugal, Qatar, Romania, Russian Federation, Saudi Arabia, Serbia, Singapore, Slovenia, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Thailand, Turkey, Ukraine, United Arab Emirates, United Kingdom, United States of America, Uzbekistan.

6.5. International: IEC/TC 117 – STE, CST

IEC/TC 117 scope

At IEC level, the technical committee **IEC/TC 117** is dedicated to CSP (concentrated solar power) and especially STE (solar thermal electricity). It is currently quite active with several standards either published, or in development: the IEC 62862 group. Despite its focus for STE, many standards are fully or partially applicable for CST. At international level, IEC/TC 117 is the most relevant committee for most SOLARIZE & EU-SOLARIS target applications. The committee official description is:

“The IEC technical committee TC 117 aims at preparing international standards for systems of Solar Thermal Electric (STE) plants for the conversion of solar thermal energy into electrical energy and for all the elements (including all sub-systems and components) in the entire STE energy system.

The standards would cover all of the current different types of systems in the STE field, as follows:

- *Parabolic trough;*
- *Solar tower;*

- *Linear Fresnel;*
- *Dish;*
- *Thermal storage.*

The standards would define terminology, design and installation requirements, performance measurement techniques and test methods, safety requirements, “power quality” issues for each of the above systems.

The standards would also address issues of connectivity and interoperability with the power grid related to connections, bidirectional communicates and centralized control (Smart Grid) and environmental aspects.

Liaisons with three TC are confirmed:

- *IEC TC 82 Solar photovoltaic energy systems*
- *ISO TC 180 Solar Energy*
- *IEA SolarPaces (Liaison A)”*

Public website for IEC/TC 117

https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:7851,25

IEC/TC 117 participants

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Countries can be either full member or associate members to IEC. The main restriction for IEC associate members is that they cannot occupy management positions and functions within the IEC and do not have voted rights in the IEC General Assembly. This status has therefore no impact on a TC participation and operation.

For each TC or WG (working group), each country has either P or O status:

- P-Members are full members who can actively participate in any technical committee or subcommittee.
- O-Members are observers who follow the work of a particular committee without committing to active participation.

Table 3 – IEC/TC 117: participating countries from SOLARIZE

SOLARIZE country	P/O status @ IEC/TC 117	IEC membership
Cyprus	Not participating	Full member
France	P-member	Full member
Germany	P-member	Full member

SOLARIZE country	P/O status @ IEC/TC 117	IEC membership
Greece	Not participating	Full member
Italy	P-member	Full member
Portugal	P-member	Full member
Spain	P-member	Full member
Turkey	Not participating	Full member

Whatever their status, here is the complete list of all 28 members to IEC/TC 117: Austria, Belgium, Chile, China, Czech Republic, Denmark, Egypt, France, Germany, Iran, Israel, Italy, Japan, Korea, Republic of, Mexico, Morocco, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russian Federation, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Arab Emirates, United Kingdom.

6.6. Europe CEN: CEN TC 312

CEN TC 312 develop standards for solar collectors, typically non-concentrating, but some standards (absorber, mechanics...) may be of interest for CSP/CST.

Current secretary is from EU-SOLARIS and SOLARIZE: CRES in Greece.

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6.7. Europe CENELEC: CLC/TC 82 and CLC/SR 117

CENELEC develop standards in the area of solar photovoltaic and thermal energy (i.e. the conversion of solar energy into heat):

- CLC/TC 82 "*solar photovoltaic energy systems*" is the European counterpart of IEC/TC 82 at CENELEC. It develops standard from the conversion of light to the interfaces to the public grid or users.
https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=305:7:0:25:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:1258463
- CLC/SR 117 "*solar thermal electric plants*" is the European counterpart of IEC/TC 117 at CENELEC.
https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=305:7:0:25:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:1258729

6.8. Spain: UNE CTN 224 (ex AEN CTN 206)

UNE CTN 224 scope

The Spanish committee AEN CTN 206 has been very active for CSP/CST/STE applications since its creation in 2010. After the split in 2017 of AENOR in AENOR (certification) and UNE (standardization), this group has been superseded in 2021 by UNE CTN 224 “Centrales termosolares” (thermosolar plants). Their work has notably been used as an initial draft for several IEC 62862 standards or project standards. The committee description is:

“Thermosolar plants, for the conversion of solar thermal energy into electricity, and for all their items (including all subsystems and components).”

International links:

- *IEC/TC 117: Solar Thermal Electricity*
- *CLC/SR 117: Solar Thermal Electricity*
- *CEN/WS NEXTOWER: Accelerated high-temperature ageing of advanced ceramic specimens for solar receivers and other concentrated solar irradiation applications.”*

Notice that “CEN/WS NEXTOWER” is a workshop from European Project NexTower (H2020 GA #721045, 2017–2021, <https://www.h2020-nextower.eu/>, coordinated by ENEA in Italy) recognized as a source by CEN for draft standard CWA 17226.

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Public website for UNE CTN 224

<https://www.une.org/encuentra-tu-norma/comites-tecnicos-de-normalizacion/comite/?c=CTN%20224>

Presentation of the committee UNE CTN 224: <https://revista.une.org/51/ctn-224-comite-une-de-centrales-termosolares.html>

6.9. Germany: DKE/K 374

DKE/K 374 “Solarthermische Anlagen zur Stromerzeugung” (Thermosolar systems for power generation) is the German counterpart for IEC/TC 117.

Public website for DKE/K 374

<https://www.dke.de/de/ueber-uns/dke-organisation-auftrag/dke-fachbereiche/dke-gremium?id=2001747&type=dke%7Cgremium>

6.10. France: AFNOR/UF82/TC 117

AFNOR/UF82/TC 117 is a subcommittee of AFNOR UF82, the group mirroring IEC/TC 82 about PV and CPV. This dedicated subcommittee mirrors IEC/TC 117.

Public website for AFNOR/UF82, including AFNOR/UF82/TC 117

<https://norminfo.afnor.org/structure/afnoruf-82/systemes-de-conversion-photovoltaique-de-lenergie-solaire/5147>

7. List of CSP/CST standards

7.1. IEC standards: IEC 62862

At IEC, the family of standards IEC 62862 is targeted for STE, however many of them are also relevant for CST. This group of standards is organized by technologies:

- **IEC 62862-1:** General STE/CST topics: terminology, solar resource, HTF, plant performance evaluation.
7 standards: 5 currently published and 2 in draft stages (1 draft cancelled pending restarting its group), 3 published standards are currently revised for a second edition.
- **IEC 62862-2:** thermal storage related.
1 standard published, 2 in draft stages.
- **IEC 62862-3:** parabolic trough targeted, but also includes mirror evaluation.
7 standards: 3 published, 4 in various draft stages (1 draft cancelled, pending restarting its group).
- **IEC 62862-4:** solar towers targeted.
3 standards: 1 published, 1 soon to be published (expected 2025-08), 1 in draft stage.
- **IEC 62862-5:** linear Fresnel targeted.
1 standard published.

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All existing project standards IEC 62862 have been listed with their stage: published standards, draft for new standards or for revision, one “cancelled” (IEC 62862-1-4 about thermal insulation, its dedicated subcommittee is currently being restarted as of 2025).

Existing stages are: published (PPUB), various draft levels (ACD > RVC > AFDIS), cancelled (CAN). See p50 for sources for stages details.

You will find abstracts for each published standards in [Annex 3](#).

Table 4 – IEC 62862 standard parts

Reference	Title	Stage
IEC TS 62862-1-1 ED2	Solar thermal electric plants - Part 1-1: Terminology	ACD

Reference	Title	Stage
IEC TS 62862-1-1:2018 ED1		PPUB
IEC TS 62862-1-2 ED2	Solar thermal electric plants – Part 1-2: General – Creation of annual solar radiation data set for solar thermal electric (STE) plant simulation	ACD
IEC TS 62862-1-2:2017 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants – Part 1-2: General – Creation of annual solar radiation data set for solar thermal electric (STE) plant simulation	PPUB
IEC TS 62862-1-3 ED2	Solar thermal electric plants – Part 1-3: General – Data format for meteorological data sets	ACD
IEC TS 62862-1-3:2017 ED1		PPUB
IEC 62862-1-4 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants – Part 1-4: Thermal insulation for solar thermal electric plants	CAN
IEC 62862-1-5:2024 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants – Part 1-5: Performance test code for solar thermal electric plants	PPUB
IEC 62862-1-6:2024 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants – Part 1-6: Silicone-based heat transfer fluids for use in line-focus concentrated solar power applications	PPUB
IEC 62862-1-7 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants – Biphenyl/ Diphenyl oxide-based heat transfer fluids for use in line-focus concentrated solar power applications	ACD
IEC TS 62862-2-1:2021 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants – Part 2-1: Thermal energy storage systems – Characterization of active, sensible systems for direct and indirect configurations	PPUB
IEC 62862-2-2 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants – Part 2-2: Thermal energy storage systems – Technical requirements for molten salt used as heat storage and heat transfer medium.	ACD
IEC 62862-2-3 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants – Part 2-3: Protocol for testing sensible and latent thermal energy storage prototypes	ACD
IEC 62862-3-1:2022 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants – Part 3-1: Systems and components – General requirements for the	PPUB

Reference	Title	Stage
	design of parabolic-trough solar thermal power plants	
IEC 62862-3-2:2018 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants - Part 3-2: Systems and components - General requirements and test methods for large-size parabolic-trough collectors	PPUB
IEC TS 62862-3-3:2020 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants - Part 3-3: Systems and components - General requirements and test methods for solar receivers	PPUB
IEC 62862-3-4 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants - Part 3-4: Code of solar field performance test for parabolic trough solar thermal power plant	CAN
IEC 62862-3-5 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants - Part 3-5: Laboratory reflectance measurement of solar reflectors	ACD
IEC 62862-3-6 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants - Part 3-6: Durability of silvered-glass reflectors - Laboratory test methods and assessment	PRVC
IEC 62862-3-7 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants - Part 3-7: Criteria for design, installation and performance verification of flexible pipe connectors in parabolic trough collector technology	ACD
IEC 62862-4-1:2022 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants - Part 4-1: General requirements for the design of solar power tower plants	PPUB
IEC 62862-4-2 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants - Part 4-2: Heliostat field control system of solar tower plants	AFDIS
IEC 62862-4-3 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants - Part 4-3: Technical requirements and design qualification of heliostats for solar power tower plants	ACD
IEC 62862-5-2:2022 ED1	Solar thermal electric plants - Part 5-2: Systems and components - General requirements and test methods for large-size linear Fresnel collectors	PPUB

7.2. Other IEC standards for CSP/CST

The interest for CSP/CST market from standards developed for PV market has not been extensively investigated for this release of this report.

Standards dedicated for CPV are listed separately [thereafter](#).

Those fields of standards for PV market could be of interest for CSP/CST:

- PV tracking evaluation may be of interest for CSP/CST, especially for low temperature process heat market.

For example: IEC 62817:2014 *"Photovoltaic systems - Design qualification of solar trackers"*.

- Electric grid connection, performance assessment... could be of interest for the STE developer.

For example: IEC 62446 *"Photovoltaic (PV) systems - Requirements for testing, documentation and maintenance - Grid connected system"*.

7.3. ISO standards to measure solar energy

There are currently no dedicated ISO standards for CSP/CST, but there are standards to measure solar energy: refer to ISO/TC 180/SC 1 work with details available at <https://www.iso.org/committee/54024/x/catalogue/>

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Below is the list of those standards from ISO/TC 180/SC 1.

Table 5 – ISO standards to measure solar energy

Reference	Title
ISO/FDIS 9059	Solar energy – Calibration of pyrheliometers by comparison to a reference pyrheliometer
ISO 9059:1990	
ISO 9060:2018	Solar energy – Specification and classification of instruments for measuring hemispherical solar and direct solar radiation
ISO 9845-1:2022	Solar energy – Reference solar spectral irradiance at the ground at different receiving conditions – Part 1: Direct normal and hemispherical solar irradiance for air mass 1,5
ISO 9846:1993	Solar energy – Calibration of a pyranometer using a pyrheliometer
ISO/FDIS 9846	
ISO 9847:2023	Solar energy – Calibration of pyranometers by comparison to a reference pyranometer

Reference	Title
ISO/TR 9901:2021	Solar energy – Pyranometers – Recommended practice for use
ISO/CD 24871-1	Solar energy – Test methods for pyranometer performance – Part 1: Response time
ISO/AWI 24871-2	Solar energy – Test methods for pyranometer performance – Part 2: Zero offset
ISO/AWI 24871-3	Solar energy – Test methods for pyranometer performance – Part 3: Non-stability
ISO/AWI 24871-4	Solar energy – Test methods for pyranometer performance – Part 4: Nonlinearity
ISO/AWI 24871-5	Solar energy – Test methods for pyranometer performance – Part 5: Directional response
ISO/AWI 24871-6	Solar energy – Test methods for pyranometer performance – Part 6: Spectral error
ISO/WD 24871-7	Solar energy – Test methods for pyranometer performance – Part 7: Temperature response
ISO/AWI 24871-8	Solar energy – Test methods for pyranometer performance – Part 8: Tilt response

7.4. Other ISO and CEN standards

There are other possible relevant standards for CSP/CST: those for solar collectors (absorbers, testing...), for buildings (glass, thermal balance...), or for plastics (optical properties, spectrum, durability...).

From the family of ISO standards for solar collectors, at least ISO 9806 does directly address CSP/CST, describing testing methods suitable for concentrating solar collectors.

Table 6 – Other ISO standard for CSP/CST

Reference	Title
ISO 9806:2017	Solar energy - Solar thermal collectors - Test methods

Refer to [Annex 1](#) for a selection of 10 such ISO standards and 18 EN standards.

7.5. International CIE standard for CSP/CST

One standard from CIE is relevant for CSP/CST, as advised by NREL:

Table 7 – International CIE standard for CSP/CST

Reference	Title
CIE TC 2-88	Standard Reference Solar Spectra for Industrial Applications

7.6. Spanish UNE standards for CSP/CST

Here is a list of the published standards by Spanish committee UNE CTN 224, with a topic similar to IEC/TC 117 and IEC 62862. Original Spanish titles have been translated in English by AI for the reader's convenience.

Table 8 – Spanish UNE standards for CSP/CST

Reference	Original title	Title (translation)
UNE 206009:2013	<i>Centrales termosolares. Terminología.</i>	Solar thermal power plants. Terminology.
UNE 206010:2015	<i>Ensayos para la verificación de las prestaciones de las centrales termosolares con tecnología de captadores cilindroparabólicos.</i>	Tests for the verification of the performance of solar thermal power plants with parabolic trough collector technology.
UNE 206011:2014	<i>Centrales termosolares. Procedimiento de generación de Año Solar Representativo.</i>	Solar thermal power plants. Representative Solar Year generation procedure.
UNE 206012:2017	<i>Caracterización del sistema de almacenamiento térmico para aplicaciones de concentración solar con captadores cilindroparabólicos.</i>	Characterization of the thermal storage system for concentrating solar power applications with parabolic trough collectors.
UNE 206013:2017	<i>Centrales termosolares. Procedimiento de generación de años percentiles de radiación solar.</i>	Solar thermal power plants. Generation procedure of solar radiation percentile years.
UNE 206014:2017	<i>Ensayos para la determinación del rendimiento del campo solar de las centrales termosolares con tecnología de captadores cilindroparabólicos.</i>	Tests to determine the performance of the solar field of solar thermal power plants

Reference	Original title	Title (translation)
		with parabolic trough technology.
UNE 206015:2018	<i>Fluidos de transferencia de calor para centrales termosolares con tecnología de captadores cilindroparabólicos. Requisitos y ensayos.</i>	Heat transfer fluids for parabolic trough solar thermal power plants. Requirements and tests.
UNE 206016:2018	<i>Paneles reflectantes para tecnologías de concentración solar.</i>	Reflective panels for concentrating solar technologies.
UNE 206017:2020	<i>Sensores específicos para la evaluación global de centrales termosolares.</i>	Specific sensors for the global evaluation of solar thermal power plants.
UNE 224001:2023	<i>Centrales termosolares. Criterios de diseño, instalación y verificación de las prestaciones de las uniones cinemáticas en las centrales termosolares con tecnología de captadores cilindroparabólicos.</i>	Solar thermal power plants. Criteria for design, installation and verification of the performance of kinematic joints in solar thermal power plants with parabolic trough collector technology.

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7.7. CSP/CST standards in other SOLARIZE countries

No national CSP/CST standards have been identified in those countries beyond transcription and eventual translation of ISO and IEC standards.

7.8. CSP/CST standards in other countries

Refer to [Annex 2](#) for CSP/CST standards in a selection of other countries out of Europe, such as China, the USA and India.

8. List of CPV standards

8.1. IEC standards for CPV

Below is the list of IEC standards for CPV market.

Table 9 – IEC standards for CPV

Reference	Title
IEC 62108:2022	Concentrator photovoltaic (CPV) modules and assemblies - Design qualification and type approval
IEC 62670-1:2013	Photovoltaic concentrators (CPV) - Performance testing - Part 1: Standard conditions
IEC 62670-2:2015	Photovoltaic concentrators (CPV) - Performance testing - Part 2: Energy measurement
IEC 62670-3:2017	Photovoltaic concentrators (CPV) - Performance testing - Part 3: Performance measurements and power rating
IEC 62787:2021	Concentrator photovoltaic (CPV) solar cells and cell on carrier (CoC) assemblies - Qualification

8.2. CLC standards for CPV

Transcription of IEC standards by CENELEC has not been included, such as EN IEC 62108:2022. The listed EN standards complements IEC standards.

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Table 10 – European CLC standards for CPV

Reference	Title
EN 62108:2016	Concentrator photovoltaic (CPV) modules and assemblies - Design qualification and type approval
EN 62670-1:2014	Photovoltaic concentrators (CPV) - Performance testing - Part 1: Standard conditions
EN 62670-2:2015	Photovoltaic concentrators (CPV) - Performance testing - Part 2: Energy measurement
EN 62670-3:2017	Photovoltaic concentrators (CPV) - Performance testing - Part 3: Performance measurements and power rating
EN 62925:2017	Concentrator photovoltaic (CPV) modules - Thermal cycling test to differentiate increased thermal fatigue durability

9. EU-SOLARIS and SOLARIZE participation to standardization

9.1. International: IEC/TC 117

In the IEC/TC 117 committee to develop the IEC 62862 standard set:

- There are 159 unique contributors worldwide.
- Among those, 66 are from EU-SOLARIS and SOLARIZE countries (68 from European Union 27 countries).
- Among those, 28 persons are from SOLARIZE or EU-SOLARIS organization members: 17% of the worldwide contributors.

There are 14 subcommittees currently listed. Their name is “PT” for each project standard with straightforward naming, for example “PT62862-2-2” for “IEC 62862-2-2”. Naming is different for “MT 1” which handles “IEC TS 62862-1-1 ED2”, and “MT 5” for “IEC TS 62862-1-2 ED2”.

Here is the participation of SOLARIZE and EU-SOLARIS organization members to currently existing IEC/TC 117 subcommittees:

Table 11 – SOLARIZE and EU-SOLARIS participation to IEC/TC 117 subcommittees

Subcommittee	CIEMAT	CENER	CNRS	DLR	ENEA	LNEG	U. Zaragoza
MT1	X	X		X	X	X	
MT5	X				X		
PT62862-1-4	X			X			
PT62862-1-5				X			
PT62862-1-6	X			X			
PT62862-1-7	X			X			
PT62862-2-2				X	X	X	
PT62862-2-3	X						
PT62862-3-4		X		X	X	X	
PT62862-3-5	X	X		X	X		X
PT62862-3-6	X	X		X	X	X	
PT62862-3-7	X			X	X		
PT62862-4-2	X		X	X	X	X	
PT62862-4-3	X			X		X	

9.2.National committees

The SOLARIZE and EU-SOLARIS partners active in IEC/TC 117 are usually also members of their national committees linked to IEC/TC 117.

9.3.Other international committees

- CRES (Greece) is active in CEN TC 312 "Thermal solar systems and components" as secretary of the committee.
- SOLARIZE and EU-SOLARIS partner's participation to ISO committees, including ISO/TC 180, has not been investigated for this release of the deliverable. Scientific work from SOLARIZE and EU-SOLARIS partners is known to have been used by those committees, but membership has not yet been identified.

10. Annex 1 – List of other international standards of interest for CSP/CST

Beyond technical general standards (ex: measuring a viscosity, applicable for a solar heat transfer fluid or any other market such as a glue), a selection of markets with nearby components for CSP/CST has been made below.

For each standard, its reference and official title has been provided, with an eventual English translation as required.

10.1. ISO and EN standards for solar collectors

Standards by ISO/TC 180/WG 3 “Collector components and materials” and ISO/TC 180/WG 4 “solar collectors” may be of interest for CSP/CST developers. ISO 9806 is of special interest as it directly includes testing methods suitable for CSP/CST.

<https://www.iso.org/committee/49070.html>

Below is a selection of standards for solar collectors’ market that may also be relevant for CSP/CST market.

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Table 12 – ISO and EN standards for solar collectors

Reference	Title
EN 12975:2022	Solar collectors – General requirements
EN 12976-1:2022	Thermal solar systems and components – Factory made systems – Part 1: General requirements
EN 12976-2:2020	Thermal solar systems and components – Factory made systems – Part 2: Test methods
EN 12977-1:2018	Thermal solar systems and components – Custom built systems – Part 1: General requirements for solar water heaters and combisystems
EN 12977-2:2018	Thermal solar systems and components – Custom built systems – Part 2: Test methods for solar water heaters and combisystems
EN 12977-3:2018	Thermal solar systems and components – Custom built systems – Part 3: Performance test methods for solar water heater stores

Reference	Title
EN 12977-4:2018	Thermal solar systems and components - Custom built systems - Part 4: Performance test methods for solar combistores
EN 12977-5:2018	Thermal solar systems and components - Custom built systems - Part 5: Performance test methods for control equipment
ISO 22975-1:2016	Solar energy - Collector components and materials - Part 1: Evacuated tubes - Durability and performance
ISO 22975-3:2014	Solar energy - Collector components and materials - Part 3: Absorber surface durability
ISO 22975-4:2023	Solar energy – Collector components and materials – Part 4: Glazing material durability and performance
ISO 22975-5:2019	Solar energy – Collector components and materials – Part 5: Insulation material durability and performance
ISO 9806:2017	Solar energy - Solar thermal collectors - Test methods

10.2. ISO and EN standards for buildings

Standards for building (glass properties and evaluation, energy balance including solar heating, lighting considerations...) may be of interest for CSP/CST developers, notably those from those committees:

- ISO/TC 59 “Buildings and civil engineering works”
<https://www.iso.org/committee/49070.html>
- CEN/TC 129 “Glass in building”
https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_I D:6111&cs=1288AE330B2D3F57B40952A625687579E

Below is a selection of standards for buildings market that may also be relevant for CSP/CST market.

Table 13 – ISO and EN standards for buildings interesting for CSP/CST

Reference	Title
EN 1096-4:2019	Glass in building - Coated glass - Part 4: Product standard
EN 14178-2:2004	Glass in building - Basic alkaline earth silicate glass products - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard

Reference	Title
EN 15193-1:2017+A1:2021	Energy performance of buildings - Energy requirements for lighting - Part 1: Specifications, Module M9
EN 15316-4-3:2017	Energy performance of buildings - Method for calculation of system energy requirements and system efficiencies - Part 4-3: Heat generation systems, thermal solar and photovoltaic systems, Module M3-8-3, M8-8-3, M11-8-3
EN 15681-2:2017	Glass in Building - Basic alumina silicate glass products - Part 2: Product standard
EN 1748-1-2:2004	Glass in building - Special basic products - Borosilicate glasses - Part 1-2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard
EN 1748-2-2:2004	Glass in building - Special basic products - Glass ceramics - Part 2-2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard
EN 17871:2024	Glass in building - Spectrophotometric characteristics of glass products - Validation procedure for calculation tool.
EN 410:2011	Glass in building - Determination of luminous and solar characteristics of glazing
EN 572-9:2004	Glass in building - Basic soda lime silicate glass products - Part 9: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard
ISO 52022-1:2017	Energy performance of buildings - Thermal, solar and daylight properties of building components and elements - Part 1: Simplified calculation method of the solar and daylight characteristics for solar protection devices combined with glazing
ISO 52022-3:2017	Energy performance of buildings - Thermal, solar and daylight properties of building components and elements - Part 3: Detailed calculation method of the solar and daylight characteristics for solar protection devices combined with glazing

10.3. ISO standards for plastics

Standards by ISO/TC 61 “Plastics” may be of interest for CSP/CST developers, especially spectral, ageing and durability considerations.

<https://www.iso.org/committee/49256.html>

For reference, the CEN counterpart is CEN/TC 249 “Plastics”.

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:6230&cs=170C05F24EF08AC268C42E03B8F786259

Table 14 – ISO standards for plastics interesting for CSP/CST

Reference	Title
ISO 877-3:2018	Plastics – Methods of exposure to solar radiation – Part 3: Intensified weathering using concentrated solar radiation
ISO/TR 17801:2017	Plastics – Standard table for reference global solar spectral irradiance at sea level – Horizontal, relative air mass 1
ISO/TR 18486:2018	Plastics – Parameters comparing the spectral irradiance of a laboratory light source for weathering applications to a reference solar spectral irradiance

11. Annex 2 – National standardization for CSP/CST in other countries

11.1. National technical committees

Here are the technical committees for non-SOLARIZE countries that may be of interest beyond European markets:

- International: International Commission on Illumination (CIE)
- In the USA, there are 4 standardization bodies related to CSP/CST:
 - American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM), in which 2 relevant committees for CSP/CST have been identified:
 - ASTM committee E44 on Solar, Geothermal and Other Alternative Energy Sources. Includes PV.
<https://www.astm.org/membership-participation/technical-committees/committee-e44>
 - ASTM subcommittee G03.09 on Radiometry: solar resource measurements and sensor calibration. Related to ISO/TC 180/SC 1.
<https://www.astm.org/membership-participation/technical-committees/committee-g03/subcommittee-g03/jurisdiction-g0309>
 - American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME)
 - ASME committee for performance test code for concentrating solar power plants (PTC 52)
<https://cstools.asme.org/csconnect/CommitteePages.cfm?Committee=100045590>
 - ASME committee for performance test code for mechanical and thermal energy storage (PTC 53), including molten salts.
<https://cstools.asme.org/csconnect/CommitteePages.cfm?Committee=100812727>
 - American National Standards Institute (ANSI). It notably distributes and endorse standards from ASTM and ASME.
 - International Code Council (ICC), is a nonprofit organization that develops and publishes standards related to building safety and fire prevention. It includes solar thermal collectors,

including concentrating, with the Solar Thermal Standard Consensus Committee (IS-STSC).

<https://www.iccsafe.org/committees/is-stsc/>

- In India: Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS). The 5 standards IS 16648 have been released in 2017. The ministry of new and renewable energy presents the efforts and market:

<https://mnre.gov.in/en/concentrated-solar-thermal/>

- Australia: CS-028 handles solar collectors, and is a link to ISO/TC 180 which it is the acting secretary.

<https://www.standards.org.au/standards-catalogue/sa-snz/standards-by-committee?committee=CS-028>

- China: the NSB is the Standardization Administration of China (SAC), 国家标准化管理委员会.

<https://www.sac.gov.cn/sacen/index.html>

- Committee TC402 "Solar Energy" is linked to ISO/TC 180 but also beyond: *The scope includes solar water heating systems, solar houses, solar cookers, solar products, solar collectors, components and other solar thermal utilization.*

https://std.samr.gov.cn/search/orgDetailView?data_id=E57C701199FA4DFDE05397BE0A0ADC4D

- Committee TC565 "Solar Thermal Power Generation" is linked to IEC/TC 117 for "solar thermal power generation technology and equipment".

https://std.samr.gov.cn/search/orgDetailView?data_id=E57C70119A894DFDE05397BE0A0ADC4D

- Committee TC540/SC2 "Climate and Climate Change Standardization Wind Energy Solar Energy" deals with wind and solar energy resources, and climate, including solar resource for CSP plants.

https://std.samr.gov.cn/search/orgDetailView?data_id=68E886FA7328E6FDE05397BE0A0A07C7

- Committee TC90 "National Solar Photovoltaic Energy System" is linked to IEC/TC 82 but does not have national project standards about CPV.

https://std.samr.gov.cn/search/orgDetailView?data_id=CFF3396241D07764E05397BE0A0A1558

11.2. Other CSP/CST national standards

India: IS 16648 by BIS

The 5 standards IS 16648 have been released in 2017 in English, and reviewed in 2022:

Table 15 – Indian standards for CSP/CST

Reference	Title
IS 16648 (Part 1):2017	Concentrated Solar Thermal – Specification Part 1 Dish Technology
IS 16648 (Part 2):2017	Concentrated Solar Thermal – Specification Part 2 Scheffler Concentrator
IS 16648 (Part 3):2017	Concentrated Solar Thermal – Specification Part 3 Parabolic Trough Concentrator
IS 16648 (Part 4):2017	Concentrated Solar Thermal – Specification Part 4 Non-Imaging Concentrator
IS 16648(Part 5):2017 and its amendment in 2019	Concentrated Solar Thermal – Specification Part 5 Test Methods

Those standards are interesting for **low temperature CST developers**. The market in India hence developed standards currently differs from usual European STE technologies: smaller facilities, linear but also dishes including Scheffler type.

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United States of America (USA), by ASTM, ASME and ICC

Those American NSB also adapt international standards from ISO and IEC, not listed below.

Table 16 – US standards for CSP/CST

Reference	Title
ASTM E2527-15(2025)	Standard Test Method for Electrical Performance of Concentrator Terrestrial Photovoltaic Modules and Systems Under Natural Sunlight
ASTM D3771-15	Standard Specification for Rubber Seals Used in Concentrating Solar Collectors
ASTM E1084-86(2015)	Standard Test Method for Solar Transmittance (Terrestrial) of Sheet Materials Using Sunlight
ASTM E1175-87(2015)	Standard Test Method for Determining Solar or Photopic Reflectance, Transmittance, and

Reference	Title
	Absorptance of Materials Using a Large Diameter Integrating Sphere
ASTM E424-71(2015)	Standard Test Methods for Solar Energy Transmittance and Reflectance (Terrestrial) of Sheet Materials
ASTM E772-15	Standard Terminology of Solar Energy Conversion
ASTM E905-87(2021)	Standard Test Method for Determining Thermal Performance of Tracking Concentrating Solar Collectors
ASTM E972-96(2013)	Standard Test Method for Solar Photometric Transmittance of Sheet Materials Using Sunlight
ASTM G130-12	Standard Test Method for Calibration of Narrow- and Broad-Band Ultraviolet Radiometers Using a Spectroradiometer
ASTM G138-12	Standard Test Method for Calibration of a Spectroradiometer Using a Standard Source of Irradiance
ASTM G167-15	Standard Test Method for Calibration of a Pyranometer Using a Pyrheliometer
ASTM G173-03(2012)	Standard Tables for Reference Solar Spectral Irradiances: Direct Normal and Hemispherical on 37°Tilted Surface
ASTM G183-15	Standard Practice for Field Use of Pyranometers, Pyrheliometers, and UV Radiometers
CIE TC 2-88	Standard Reference Solar Spectra for Industrial Applications
ICC 901/SRCC 100-2015	Standard for Solar Thermal Collectors

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China, by SAC

Below is a selection of 38 standards for CSP/CST market.

Table 17 – Chinese standards for CSP/CST

Reference	Original title	Title (translation)
20231000-T-469	槽式太阳能集热管 热损系数测试方法	Test method for heat loss coefficient of trough solar collector

Reference	Original title	Title (translation)
20241801-T-524	塔式太阳能光热发电站镜场控制系统技术规范	Technical Specifications for Mirror Field Control System of Tower Solar Thermal Power Station
20251268-T-524	槽式太阳能光热发电站运行规程	Parabolic Trough Solar Thermal Power Plant Operation Procedures
DL/T 5628-2021	太阳能热发电厂岩土工程勘察规程	Geotechnical Engineering Investigation Specification for Solar Thermal Power Plant
GB/T 14890-1994	工作直接日射表的校准方法	Calibration Method of Working Direct Pyrheliometer
GB/T 26972-2011	聚光型太阳能热发电术语	Concentrated Solar Thermal Power Generation Terminology
GB/T 40099-2021	太阳能光热发电站代表年太阳辐射数据集的生成方法	Method for generating representative annual solar radiation dataset for solar thermal power plants
GB/T 40102-2021	太阳能热发电站接入电力系统检测规程	Testing procedures for solar thermal power station connection to power system
GB/T 40103-2021	太阳能热发电站接入电力系统技术规定	Technical regulations for connecting solar thermal power stations to the power system
GB/T 40104-2021	太阳能光热发电站术语	Terminology of solar thermal power station
GB/T 40614-2021	光热发电站性能评估技术要求	Technical requirements for performance evaluation of CSP plants
GB/T 40703-2021	太阳能中温工业热利用系统设计规范	Design specification for medium-temperature industrial heat utilization systems using solar energy

Reference	Original title	Title (translation)
GB/T 40821-2021	太阳能热发电站换热系统检测规范	Specification for testing heat exchange system of solar thermal power station
GB/T 40858-2021	太阳能光热发电站集热管通用要求与测试方法	General requirements and test methods for collector tubes of solar thermal power stations
GB/T 40866-2021	太阳能光热发电站调度命名规则	Solar thermal power station dispatch naming rules
GB/T 41087-2021	太阳能热发电站换热系统技术要求	Technical requirements for heat exchange system of solar thermal power station
GB/T 41303-2022	塔式太阳能热发电站吸热器技术要求	Technical requirements for receivers of tower solar thermal power plants
GB/T 41307-2022	塔式太阳能热发电站吸热器检测方法	Tower solar thermal power station absorber detection method
GB/T 41308-2022	太阳能热发电站储热系统性能评价导则	Guidelines for performance evaluation of thermal storage systems in solar thermal power plants
GB/T 41992-2022	太阳能热发电站运行指标评价导则	Guidelines for evaluation of operating indicators of solar thermal power plants
GB/T 44079-2024	塔式太阳能光热发电站运行规程	Tower solar thermal power station operation procedures
GB/T 44140-2024	塔式太阳能光热发电站定日镜技术要求	Technical requirements for heliostats in tower solar thermal power stations
GB/T 44222-2024	塔式太阳能光热发电站集热系统技术要求	Technical requirements for the collection system of tower solar thermal power stations

Reference	Original title	Title (translation)
GB/T 44788-2024	太阳能光热发电站 并网调度运行技术 要求	Technical requirements for grid-connected dispatching and operation of solar thermal power stations
GB/T 44800-2024	太阳能光热发电站 储热/传热用工作介 质技术要求 熔融盐	Technical requirements for working medium for heat storage/heat transfer in solar thermal power plants Molten salt
GB/T 45234.302-2025	太阳能热发电站 第 3-2部分：系统与部 件 大尺寸抛物面槽 式集热器通用要求 与测试方法	Solar thermal power plants Part 3-2: Systems and components General requirements and test methods for large parabolic trough collectors
GB/T 45310-2025	塔式太阳能光热发 电站主控制系统技 术条件	Technical requirements for main control system of tower solar thermal power station
GB/T 45313-2025	太阳能光热发电站 熔融盐储热系统技 术要求	Technical requirements for molten salt heat storage system in solar thermal power station
GB/T 45427-2025	光热电站太阳能资 源评估规范	Specification for Solar Energy Resource Assessment of Concentrated Solar Power Plants
GB/Z 40104.103-2023	太阳能光热发电站 第1-3部分：通用气 象数据集数据格式	Solar thermal power station Part 1-3: Common meteorological data set data format
GB/Z 45115-2024	太阳能光热发电站 直接与间接式主动 显热储热系统特性	Characteristics of direct and indirect active sensible heat storage systems in solar thermal power plants
JB/T 12238-2015	聚光光伏太阳能发 电模组的测试方法	Test methods for concentrated photovoltaic solar power generation modules

Reference	Original title	Title (translation)
JB/T 14689-2024	塔式太阳能光热发电跟踪回转传动装置	Tower type solar thermal power generation tracking rotary transmission device
NB/T 10972-2022	塔式太阳能热发电厂集热系统设计规范	Design specification for solar thermal tower power plant collector system
NB/T 10973-2022	太阳能热发电厂发电量及厂用电率计算导则	Guidelines for calculation of power generation and power consumption rate of solar thermal power plants
NB/T 10974-2022	线性菲涅耳式太阳能热发电厂集热系统设计规范	Design specification for linear Fresnel solar thermal power plant collector system
NB/T 11166-2023	太阳能热发电厂吸热塔结构设计规范	Specification for the structural design of heat absorption towers in solar thermal power plants
NB/T 11176-2023	太阳能热发电项目监测评估规程	Monitoring and evaluation procedures for solar thermal power generation projects

12. Annex 3 – Abstracts of all published IEC 62862 standards

For the abstracts of the other standards listed in this report: refer to their NSB or contact the author of this report.

12.1. IEC TS 62862-1-1:2018

Solar thermal electric plants – Part 1-1: Terminology

IEC TS 62862-1-1:2018(E) contains the main terms and definitions used by the solar thermal electric (STE) industry and intends to be a reference for users of industry documents. Since the components and configurations of STE plants depend on the concentrating solar thermal technology used (i.e., central receiver, parabolic-trough collector, parabolic-dish or linear Fresnel concentrator), some terms are not applicable to all types of STE plants and notes have been introduced in their definitions for clarification.

12.2. IEC TS 62862-1-2:2017

Solar thermal electric plants – Part 1-2: General – Creation of annual solar radiation data set for solar thermal electric (STE) plant simulation

IEC TS 62862-1-2:2017(E) defines the procedures for the creation of annual solar radiation data sets (ASR) for solar thermal electricity (STE) plant simulation. This document defines procedures needed for the ASR construction as well as its components and parameters. The scope of application of this document refers to the needs associated with solar thermal power plant projects and mainly related to the simulation of an annual period with a solar radiation sum close to a normal annual value (from among an estimation of all possible annual values).

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12.3. IEC TS 62862-1-3:2017

Solar thermal electric plants – Part 1-3: General – Data format for meteorological data sets

IEC TS 62862-1-3:2017(E) defines a data format for meteorological data sets. The goal of this document is to reduce efforts for data exchange and to avoid errors caused by misunderstandings due to the application of various different and at times unclear formats.

12.4. IEC 62862-1-5:2024

Solar thermal electric plants – Part 1-3: General – Data format for meteorological data sets

IEC 62862-1-5:2024 provide procedures and guidelines to carry out acceptance tests for solar thermal power plants, of any concentration technology, with the uncertainty level given in ISO/IEC Guide 98-3.

This document establishes the measurements, instrumentation and techniques required for determining the following performance parameters for a given period:

- *available solar radiation energy,*
- *plant electricity consumptions,*
- *net electricity generation,*
- *non-solar energy,*
- *net plant efficiency.*

This document specifies the characteristics of a calculation tool that serves as a reference for expected electricity production during the test period and under real-time solar irradiance and other meteorological data.

This document is applicable to solar thermal power plants of any size using any concentration technology, where the sun is the main source of energy, and all elements and systems are operative. Such power plants can optionally have non-solar energy sources, such as natural gas or other renewable energies, and a thermal storage system.

This document is applicable to acceptance testing in such power plants, as well as in any other scenario in which their performance must be known."

12.5. IEC 628621-6:2024

Solar thermal electric plants – Part 1-6: Silicone-based heat transfer fluids for use in line-focus concentrated solar power applications

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IEC 628621-6:2024 specifies the technical requirements (safety and physical parameters), test methods, inspection rules and intervals, sampling, judgment, marking, labelling and accompanying documents, packaging, transportation and storage, recycling and disposal of silicone-based heat transfer fluids (SiHTF) for use in line-focusing solar thermal power plants.

The application of polydimethylsiloxane-based heat transfer fluids for this type of installation is covered in this document. Owing to their chemical nature and composition, the introduction of new test methods to determine the applicability and the thermal stability of SiHTF is included in this document.

12.6. IEC TS 62862-2-1:2021

Solar thermal electric plants – Part 2-1: Thermal energy storage systems – Characterization of active, sensible systems for direct and indirect configurations

IEC TS 62862-2-1:2021 defines the requirements and the test methods for the characterization of thermal energy storage (TES) systems. This document contains the information necessary for determining the performance and functional characteristics of

active direct and indirect thermal energy storage systems based on sensible heat in solar thermal power plants using parabolic-trough collector, Fresnel collector or tower central receiver technology with liquid storage media.

This document includes characterization procedures for testing energy storage system charge and discharge, as well as reporting the results. Test performance requirements are given and the instrumentation necessary for them, as well as data acquisition and processing methods and methods for calculating the results and their uncertainties.

12.7. IEC 62862-3-1:2022

Solar thermal electric plants - Part 3-1: Systems and components - General requirements for the design of parabolic-trough solar thermal power plants

IEC 62862-3-1:2022 specifies the general requirements for the design of parabolic-trough solar thermal power plants. It includes requirements for the electric power system, solar resource assessment, site selection, overall planning, collector system, heat transfer system, thermal energy storage system, steam generation system, steam turbine system, layout of solar field, layout of power block, electrical equipment and system, water treatment system, instrumentation and control, auxiliary system and ancillary facilities, as well as considerations concerning health and safety.

This document is applicable to the design of new, expanded or rebuilt parabolic-trough solar thermal power plants using a steam turbine.

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12.8. IEC 62862-3-2:2018

Solar thermal electric plants - Part 3-2: Systems and components - General requirements and test methods for large-size parabolic-trough collectors

IEC 62862-3-2:2018 specifies the requirements and the test methods for the characterization of a large-size parabolic-trough collector. This document covers the determination of optical and thermal performance of parabolic-trough collectors, and the tracking accuracy of the collector one-axis tracking system. This test method is for outdoor testing only. This document applies to parabolic-trough collectors equipped with the manufacturer-supplied sun tracking mechanism.

12.9. IEC TS 62862-3-3:2020

Solar thermal electric plants - Part 3-3: Systems and components - General requirements and test methods for solar receivers

IEC TS 62862-3-3:2020 specifies the technical requirements, tests, durability and technical performance parameters of solar thermal receivers for absorbing concentrated solar radiation and transferring the heat to a fluid used in concentrated solar thermal power plants with linear-focus solar collectors. The receivers addressed consist of an absorber tube and an insulating glass envelope tube.

This document includes the definitions of technical properties and characterization of geometry and performance parameters as well as the test methods for optical characterization, heat loss, and durability. For the sake of clarity, it is stated here that the thermal loss tests described in this document do not deliver the thermal loss of the receiver tubes when they are installed in commercial solar fields.

12.10. IEC 62862-4-1:2022

Solar thermal electric plants - Part 4-1: General requirements for the design of solar power tower plants

IEC 62862-4-1:2022 specifies the general requirements for the design of solar power tower plants and covers the electric power system requirements, the solar resource assessment, the site selection, the overall planning, the layout of the heliostat field and the receiver tower, the layout of the power block, the collector system, the heat transfer, the thermal energy storage and steam generation system, the steam turbine system, the water treatment system, the information system, instrumentation and control, the electrical equipment and system, occupational safety and occupational health. This document is applicable to the design requirements of newly built, expanded or rebuilt solar power tower plants employing steam turbines with molten salt or water-steam as heat transfer fluid.

12.11. IEC 62862-5-2:2022

Solar thermal electric plants - Part 5-2: Systems and components - General requirements and test methods for large-size linear Fresnel collectors

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IEC 62862-5-2:2022 specifies the requirements and the test methods for the characterization of a large-size linear Fresnel collector.

This document covers the determination of optical and thermal performance of linear Fresnel collectors, and the tracking accuracy of the collector one-axis tracking system. This test method is for outdoor testing only.

This document applies to linear Fresnel collectors according to Annex A equipped with the manufacturer-supplied sun tracking mechanism.

This document applies to the whole collector field in-situ or as a minimum unit to be tested to an individual collector string (loop) connected to the main piping (flow, return flow) to and from a heat sink, covering the full temperature range of the field.

13. Annex 4 – Additional Resources

13.1. IEC codes and practices (also applicable to ISO)

- List of IEC standards stage codes such as CAN, AFDIS, PPUB...:
<https://www.iec.ch/standards-development/stage-codes>
- List of the 186 main IEC acronyms:
<https://www.iec.ch/news-resources/reference-material#codes>
- How to write a standard, or “Principles and rules for the structure and drafting of ISO and IEC documents”:
https://www.iec.ch/system/files/2023-09/isoiecdir2%7Bed9.0%7D_en.pdf

13.2. List of standards for SHIP

A similar work as this report but focused on solar heat integration in industrial processes (SHIP) has been presented at SolarPACES 30th conference in 2024: “*Summary of Standardization for Concentrating Solar plants in Industrial Processes*” by Fabienne Sallaberry and al with a focus on European and Spanish activities. At the time of writing of this document, the DOI was still pending. The publication was planned by TIB Open Publishing: you should be able to get this PDF proceedings from the list of works of the main author Fabienne Sallaberry (CENER): [ORCID ID 0000-0003-1317-6315](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1317-6315).

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13.3. EU-SOLARIS

Public website: <https://eu-solaris.eu/>

Members (June 2025):

- **Spain:** CIEMAT, CENER, IMDEA, U. DE LLEIDA, U. POLITÈCNICA DE CATALUNYA, CIC ENERGIGUNE, TEKNIKER, U. NACIONAL DE EDUCACIÓN A DISTANCIA (UNED), U. POLITÈCNICA DE MADRID, UC3M, U. DE ALMERÍA
- **France:** CNRS
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- **Greece:** CRES, CERTH